

USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES AT PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada boshlang‘ich ta‘limda xorijiy tillarni o‘qitishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish va uning tilni o‘zlashtirish jarayonini tezlashtirish samaradorligi jahon tadqiqotchilarining ishlaridan foydalangan holda o‘rganiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Raqamli texnologiya, til o‘zlashtirish, interaktiv, videokonferensaloqa, vazifaga asoslangan faoliyat, o‘rganishga jalb qilish

Abstract. In this article, the usage of digital technologies in teaching foreign languages at primary education and its efficiency to accelerate the process of language acquisition will be investigated by using world researchers’ works

Keywords: Digital technology, language acquisition, interactive, videoconferencing, task-based activities, learning engagement

Аннотация. В данной статье на основе работ мировых исследователей будет исследовано использование цифровых технологий при обучении иностранным языкам в начальной школе и их эффективность для ускорения процесса овладения языком. Другие соответствующие понятия и термины будут оцениваться на основе определений, данных мировыми учеными.

Ключевые слова: цифровые технологии, овладение языком, интерактивность, видеоконференции, деятельность, основанная на выполнении задач, вовлеченность в обучение.

There has been considerable growth in foreign language and second language learning and it is presumably due to the current demand for international communication and relationship among countries. Learning a foreign language will be asset and offers a wide range of opportunities for language learners in their future career. Although immersing in a new language gives myriad of chances, learners will definitely face new challenges in terms of adaptation in a new language atmosphere and daily usage. It should be admitted that, many countries’ language teaching used to focus on grammar translation method. Students at school used to read long texts and translate them. In this way, they can only improve vocabulary range and translation skills. Although the method has beneficial sides for learners, globalization has made people to be more interactive and language proficient. Consequently, a new era of teaching has begun which includes more use of new technologies and methods in teaching. This definitely prompted pedagogical experiments to find new efficient ways to accelerate learning process. Fortunately, with the advent of modern technologies in education, considerable burden of studies has been eased and enabled learners to accelerate language acquisition process. Firstly, those educational tools can easily engage learners in learning process as they are creative and motivational. To be more specific, a child may be bored from the same daily routine and the advent of sophisticated technologies encourages them to be more active and interactive. As technological gadgets have become an integral part of our daily life, even young learners can be engaged easily in technology based lessons. The use of information and communication technologies is closely integrated with incorporating digital media in foreign language learning and was originally closely related to individualized computer-

based drills and practice activities aimed at supporting learning in mastering grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation.[1] There are many educational technology tools in teaching sphere and they are actively being implemented at classrooms. One technology that has proved popular and an effective tool in teaching/learning in the second language classroom is the Interactive Whiteboard (IWB) [2] The visual aspect of the IWB appears to be the primary reason for active motivated engagement in the learning process. [3] This type of technology can be used to provide opportunities for children to actively engage in different activities for different purposes. [4] Currently, Interactive Whiteboards are being used nearly in all educational institutions. Primary education system is not exception in this context. What Interactive Whiteboard offers is many. As it is multi-functional, learners can use it as a plain blackboard, video screen or to present Power point slides. Different types of educational games related to digital appliances can be played on the board. To demonstrate, Kahoot game can be played through Interactive Whiteboard.

It is undoubtedly true that early childhood education means a lot of challenges to be facilitated in all teaching spheres. Teaching a foreign language at schools can be both challenging and interesting for language teachers. To be more precise, communication and writing digital tools can engage whole audience in learning process regardless their age and interest. One of the most popular digital teaching aids is “Kahoot” platform. This program helps teachers to organize questionnaires based on topics. Furthermore, this platform can be widely used at primary education at any grades. This is because, an instructor can make a picture based tests also and this will enhance elementary pupils to sharpen their knowledge considerably. For instance, if the topic of 5th grade students is “naming domestic animals”, the Kahoot platform allows its users to make tests with photos. This presumably helps visual learners to comprehend the topic more effectively. Another advantage of the platform is that, it is competition based educational tool which increases the interest level of learners. Students have to gain balls according to the number of correct answers and at the end of the test, the first three participants in the podium will be announced. Getting higher score will be stimulation for nearly all students in class regardless their language proficiency.

The visual aspect occupies a special place in the educational process. Visualization is the process of presenting data using images, while its aim is to maximize the ease of understanding; the visible form can be applied to any conceivable object, subject or process etc. Jan Comenius was one of the first scholars to pay attention to the visualization principle in education, emphasizing the fact that it was one of the most important tools in the learning process. The importance of visualization was also asserted by another Russian teacher, Ushinskij, who described it as a tool reflecting on individual learners’ characteristics. Ushinskij emphasized the fact that visualization makes learning more accessible, specific and interesting, representing a factor preventing feelings of exhaustion and fatigue.[5] It is well-known fact that there are different types of learners and one of them visual learners. As Ushinskij mentioned above, learning something new with the help of visual aids such as images or real objects, the efficiency will be higher. To demonstrate, it is highly recommended to apply visual tools at primary schools as the pupils are taking their first step into the real world. In order to have deeper understanding about animals and their appearances, it is effective to instruct them with real pictures. This will absolutely broaden their horizons and ease learning process.

Learning a foreign language requires that students have regular contact with the language outside the classroom as well. The Internet contains several free reading and listening resources

that can be used for individual language practice at home. The possibilities of using Web 2.0 technologies are numerous, so that many websites offer reading and listening activities at various levels. [4] This presumably means a learner should be engaged in language acquisition process both inside and outside of the classroom. This is because, the intake during classroom can be high but if the knowledge is not practiced regularly it will not bring any progress. One of the most commonly used free listening resources can be found at **dailydictation.com**. This platform includes listening tasks and learners need to write what they listen, write and check their work. As it is online educational tool, it can be applied both at school and home. At the same time, there are some language learners who are introvert learners and prefer autonomous learning. Digital educational tools can be applied in groups and individually. Outside learning will be asset in their progress for the pupils who are not willing to share their language acquisition process in class at school.

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